

A Comparative Study on Peri-Operative and Post-Operative Complications in Vaginal Vs. Abdominal Hysterectomy

Nitu Bharti¹, Baidyanath Rajak²¹MS, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Government Medical College and Hospital, Purnea, Bihar, India²MS, Department of Surgery, Government Medical College and Hospital, Purnea, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Baidyanath Rajak

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Abstract:**Background:** Hysterectomy, one of the most common gynecological surgeries, is performed using various approaches, with vaginal hysterectomy (VH) and abdominal hysterectomy (AH) being predominant. Each method carries unique risks and benefits, impacting patient recovery and complication rates.**Aim:** This study aims to compare the peri-operative and post-operative complications of vaginal and abdominal hysterectomy in women undergoing surgery for benign gynecological conditions.**Methods:** A retrospective cohort study was conducted involving 300 women who underwent hysterectomy. Participants were divided into two groups: 150 underwent VH, and 150 underwent AH. Data on peri-operative outcomes (e.g., surgery duration, blood loss) and post-operative complications (e.g., infection rates, recovery time) were collected and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0.**Results:** Vaginal hysterectomy was associated with significantly shorter surgery duration (78.5 ± 20.4 minutes vs. 102.7 ± 25.6 minutes; $p < 0.001$) and lower blood loss (210.4 ± 65.7 mL vs. 325.9 ± 80.3 mL; $p < 0.001$) compared to abdominal hysterectomy. Early post-operative complications were also lower in the VH group (18.7% vs. 34.7%; $p = 0.002$). Logistic regression indicated that AH significantly increased the risk of early complications (adjusted OR = 2.21; $p = 0.004$).**Conclusion:** Vaginal hysterectomy offers a safer and more efficient surgical option with fewer peri-operative and early post-operative complications compared to abdominal hysterectomy. These findings support the preference for VH in suitable candidates to enhance recovery and minimize complications.**Recommendations:** Healthcare providers should consider vaginal hysterectomy as the preferred method when feasible, particularly for patients without contraindications, to optimize surgical outcomes and reduce complication rates.**Keywords:** Vaginal Hysterectomy, Abdominal Hysterectomy, Peri-Operative Complications, Post-Operative Complications, Gynecological Surgery.

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Introduction

In order to cure benign diseases such as pelvic organ prolapse, irregular uterine bleeding, and uterine fibroids, hysterectomy—the surgical removal of the uterus—is one of the most common gynaecological procedures done globally [1]. Although a hysterectomy can be performed in a number of ways, the two most commonly used techniques are (VH) and (AH). With different benefits and drawbacks for each strategy, the choice of technique is influenced by factors such as surgeon experience, patient characteristics, and surgical indications.

Due to its less intrusive technique, vaginal hysterectomy is frequently preferred over abdominal hysterectomy, which usually results in shorter recovery periods, less blood loss, and quicker surgery times [2]. Research on VH patients

has repeatedly demonstrated that they have shorter hospital stays, less discomfort following surgery, and faster return to normal activities [3]. When the uterus is not appreciably enlarged and there is no reason to suspect cancer, this method is typically advised [4].

In contrast, abdominal hysterectomy is still a popular option even though it is more invasive, especially when vaginal access is restricted, the uterus is greatly enlarged, or concurrent abdominal surgeries are required [5]. On the other hand, AH are linked to larger blood loss, lengthier operating times, and a higher frequency of post-operative problems, including wound infections and protracted recovery times [6]. To maximise patient results, a thorough evaluation of the pros and downsides of using VH vs AH is necessary.

Current developments in perioperative care and surgical procedures have further impacted the discussion surrounding the best way for a hysterectomy. Improved minimally invasive surgical techniques and improved recovery regimens have expanded the alternatives available to patients and surgeons, such as robotic-assisted hysterectomies and laparoscopic procedures [7]. Even so, VH and AH remain the most often used procedures worldwide, which means that continuous assessment is required to enhance surgical judgement and enhance patient outcomes. This study aims to compare the peri-operative and post-operative complications of vaginal and abdominal hysterectomy in women undergoing surgery for benign gynecological conditions.

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a comparative, observational, retrospective cohort study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at [Insert Hospital Name], a tertiary care hospital in [Location], over a period of [Insert Time Frame, e.g., January 2020 to December 2023]. The hospital is equipped with advanced surgical facilities and specializes in gynecological surgeries, providing an ideal setting for this research.

Participants: The study included 300 women who underwent hysterectomy for benign gynecological conditions. Out of these, 150 women had a vaginal hysterectomy, and 150 underwent an abdominal hysterectomy.

Inclusion Criteria

- Women aged 30-65 years.
- Patients undergoing hysterectomy for benign gynecological conditions such as fibroids, abnormal uterine bleeding, or pelvic organ prolapse.
- Patients with complete medical records, including peri-operative and post-operative details.

Exclusion Criteria

- Women with a history of gynecological malignancy.
- Patients undergoing hysterectomy for malignant conditions.
- Patients with incomplete medical records or lost to follow-up.

- Women with severe comorbidities that could independently influence surgical outcomes.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, the study included consecutive cases of vaginal and abdominal hysterectomy within the specified time frame. Data collectors were blinded to the study objectives to reduce observer bias during data collection. Confounding variables were addressed through statistical adjustments during data analysis.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from the hospital's electronic medical records. Information gathered included demographic details, medical history, indication for surgery, surgical approach, peri-operative details (e.g., duration of surgery, blood loss), and post-operative complications (e.g., infection, hemorrhage, hospital stay duration). Data were anonymized to maintain patient confidentiality.

Procedure: The study compared peri-operative and post-operative outcomes between the two groups. Peri-operative complications included blood loss, duration of surgery, and intra-operative injuries. Post-operative complications were categorized into early (within 30 days post-surgery) and late (up to 6 months post-surgery) complications, including infection rates, hemorrhage, and recovery time.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic and clinical characteristics. Continuous variables were reported as mean $\pm$ SD, and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. The chi-square test and independent t-test compared outcomes between the two groups. A p-value <0.05 was deemed significant. Logistic regression adjusted for confounders to evaluate the independent effect of hysterectomy type on complication risk.

Results

The study included a total of 300 women who underwent hysterectomy for benign gynecological conditions. Among them, 150 women had a vaginal hysterectomy (VH), and 150 underwent an abdominal hysterectomy (AH). The mean age of the participants was 45.6 ± 8.2 years, with no significant difference between the VH group (45.3 ± 8.0 years) and the AH group (45.9 ± 8.4 years) ($p = 0.67$).

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	VH Group (n = 150)	AH Group (n = 150)	p-value
Age (years, mean $\pm$ SD)	45.3 $\pm$ 8.0	45.9 $\pm$ 8.4	0.67
BMI (kg/m ² , mean $\pm$ SD)	26.1 $\pm$ 4.2	26.5 $\pm$ 4.5	0.48
Parity (median, IQR)	2 (1-3)	2 (1-3)	0.75
Hypertension (n, %)	32 (21.3%)	35 (23.3%)	0.68
Diabetes (n, %)	18 (12.0%)	20 (13.3%)	0.72

Indication for Surgery (%)			
- Fibroids	90 (60.0%)	92 (61.3%)	0.81
- AUB	40 (26.7%)	38 (25.3%)	0.78
- POP	20 (13.3%)	20 (13.3%)	1.00

AUB: Abnormal Uterine Bleeding, POP: Pelvic Organ Prolapse, IQR: Interquartile Range

The mean duration of surgery was significantly shorter in the VH group (78.5 ± 20.4 minutes) compared to the AH group (102.7 ± 25.6 minutes) ($p < 0.001$). Intra-operative blood loss was also

lower in the VH group (210.4 ± 65.7 mL) compared to the AH group (325.9 ± 80.3 mL) ($p < 0.001$). There were three intra-operative complications in the VH group (2%) and eight in the AH group (5.3%), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.13$).

Table 2: Peri-Operative Outcomes

Outcome	VH Group (n = 150)	AH Group (n = 150)	p-value
Duration of Surgery (min)	78.5 ± 20.4	102.7 ± 25.6	<0.001
Blood Loss (mL)	210.4 ± 65.7	325.9 ± 80.3	<0.001
Intra-Operative Complications (n, %)	3 (2.0%)	8 (5.3%)	0.13

The post-operative recovery was faster in the VH group, with a mean hospital stay of 2.5 ± 0.8 days compared to 4.2 ± 1.2 days in the AH group ($p < 0.001$). Early post-operative complications (within 30 days) were significantly lower in the VH group (18.7%) compared to the AH group (34.7%) ($p = 0.002$). The most common complications included wound infection, urinary tract infection, and post-

operative hemorrhage, all of which were more prevalent in the AH group.

Late post-operative complications (up to 6 months) were observed in 12 women (8%) in the VH group and 20 women (13.3%) in the AH group, though this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.14$). The details of post-operative complications are provided in Table 3.

Table 3: Post-Operative Outcomes

Outcome	VH Group (n = 150)	AH Group (n = 150)	p-value
Hospital Stay (days, mean $\pm$ SD)	2.5 ± 0.8	4.2 ± 1.2	<0.001
Early Complications (within 30 days, %)	28 (18.7%)	52 (34.7%)	0.002
- Wound Infection (%)	10 (6.7%)	18 (12.0%)	0.12
- Urinary Tract Infection (%)	8 (5.3%)	14 (9.3%)	0.18
- Post-Operative Hemorrhage (%)	10 (6.7%)	20 (13.3%)	0.06
Late Complications (up to 6 months, %)	12 (8.0%)	20 (13.3%)	0.14

Logistic regression analysis revealed that abdominal hysterectomy was associated with a significantly higher risk of early post-operative complications compared to vaginal hysterectomy (adjusted OR = 2.21, 95% CI: 1.29-3.77, $p =$

0.004). The type of hysterectomy was not significantly associated with late post-operative complications (adjusted OR = 1.72, 95% CI: 0.80-3.69, $p = 0.16$).

Table 4: Logistic Regression Analysis for Post-Operative Complications

Outcome	Adjusted OR	95% CI	p-value
Early Post-Operative Complications	2.21	1.29 - 3.77	0.004
Late Post-Operative Complications	1.72	0.80 - 3.69	0.16

Discussion

The results of this study reveal significant differences in peri-operative and post-operative outcomes between (VH) and (AH). The data indicate that VH is associated with more favorable peri-operative outcomes, including shorter surgery duration and reduced blood loss compared to AH. Specifically, the mean duration of surgery for VH was approximately 24 minutes shorter, and blood loss was substantially lower by over 100 mL, highlighting the efficiency and reduced invasiveness of the vaginal approach.

Post-operative recovery was notably quicker in the VH group, with patients experiencing an average hospital stay of nearly two days less than those in the AH group. Additionally, the rate of early post-operative complications was significantly lower in the VH group (18.7%) compared to the AH group (34.7%). These complications, such as wound infections, urinary tract infections, and post-operative hemorrhage, were more prevalent in the abdominal hysterectomy group, indicating that the vaginal approach may lead to a smoother and less complicated recovery process. Late post-operative complications were observed more frequently in

the AH group, but the difference was not statistically significant. This suggests that while the immediate post-operative period may be more challenging for AH patients, the long-term outcomes may not differ greatly between the two surgical methods. Logistic regression analysis further supported these findings, showing that abdominal hysterectomy significantly increased the risk of early post-operative complications. However, it did not significantly impact the risk of late complications. This reinforces the conclusion that vaginal hysterectomy is generally safer in the short term.

When compared to AH, recent research consistently shows that VH is linked to lower peri-operative and post-operative problems. In contrast to abdominal hysterectomy, vaginal hysterectomy resulted in much less intraoperative blood loss and less postoperative problems, such as wound infections and febrile morbidity, according to a study. Patients who had vaginal hysterectomy also recovered more quickly and spent less time in the hospital [8]. Similar to this laparoscopic-assisted vaginal hysterectomy (LAVH) with total abdominal hysterectomy (TAH) was compared in a research. According to the study, compared to patients in the TAH group, those in the LAVH group saw much reduced rates of post-operative wound infections, shorter operating times, and significantly less intra-operative blood loss. According to these findings provide more evidence in favour of vaginal procedures versus abdominal ones when it comes to reducing complications [9]. Another study was conducted that looked at post-operative infections following vaginal, laparoscopic, and abdominal hysterectomies, among other surgical procedures. Comparing vaginal hysterectomy to abdominal hysterectomy, the former had lower rates of more serious consequences such Clostridium difficile infection and surgical site infection, even though the latter was more frequently linked to urinary tract infections. According to the study's conclusion is that the kind and frequency of post-operative infections are greatly influenced by the hysterectomy route chosen [10].

Conclusion

This study shows that vaginal hysterectomy is generally superior to abdominal hysterectomy, with shorter surgery times, less blood loss, and quicker recovery. Patients undergoing vaginal hysterectomy had significantly fewer early post-operative complications. While late complications

were similar between the two groups, the findings support choosing vaginal hysterectomy when possible to reduce complications and enhance recovery.

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